

SCIANCE

D1.3

Mapping Methodology

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Abstract

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The SCIANCE Mapping Methodology provides a structured, scalable, and evidence-based approach to analysing the European landscape of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Science.

The mapping approach combines semi-automated data analytics with expert validation and focuses on three interrelated dimensions: (i) key actors involved in AI-enabled scientific research, (ii) relevant research and innovation infrastructures, and (iii) emerging trends in AI adoption across scientific domains. The analysis thematically covers five scientific pilot domains—Astronomy & Physics, Materials Science, Earth Sciences, Life Sciences, and Social Sciences & Humanities—alongside cross-cutting AI research and innovations that support the scientific process.

At the core of the methodology is the OpenAIRE Graph, which serves as a trusted and interoperable backbone linking publications, datasets, software, projects, organisations, and services. A dedicated data pipeline enables systematic data collection, stratification, and enrichment, complemented by the automated detection of AI technologies in scientific texts, technology-application pairing, Technology Readiness Level estimation, and multi-dimensional trend and ecosystem analyses.

In addition, the deliverable defines the methodology for establishing the SCIANCE Good Practices Registry. Using a two-stage design—case identification and in-depth qualitative analysis based on a Context–Mechanism–Outcome framework—the registry documents empirically grounded, transferable examples of effective and responsible AI-enabled scientific practices.

Overall, the methodology supports SCIANCE’s strategic objective of strengthening Europe’s leadership in AI-enabled scientific research by underpinning the project’s Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, infrastructure roadmap, and policy recommendations.

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Terminology / Acronyms	
ADRA	AI Data Robotics Association
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
CAIRNE	Confederation of Laboratories for Artificial Intelligence Research in Europe
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
ELLIS	European Laboratory for Learning and Intelligent Systems
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FoS	Field of Science
GAN	General Adversarial Network
GNN	Graph Neural Network
LLM	Large Language Model
MeSH	Medical Subject Headings
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
NASA ADS	NASA Astrophysics Data System
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VAE	Variational Autoencoder

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable at hand presents the **SCIANCE Mapping Methodology**, which underpins the systematic analysis of the European landscape of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in and for Science. As shown in Section 2, mapping in SCIANCE effectively supports the project’s overarching objective of strengthening Europe’s leadership in AI-enabled scientific research by providing an evidence-based foundation for the project’s Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, infrastructure roadmap, and policy recommendations.

Section 3 illustrates the overall **mapping methodology employed by SCIANCE**. The project adopts a structured, semi-automated, and scalable approach, combining advanced data analytics with expert validation. It focuses on three interconnected dimensions: (i) key actors involved in AI-enabled scientific research in the EU-27 and associated countries, (ii) relevant research and innovation infrastructures in the EU-27 and associated countries, and (iii) emerging trends in AI adoption across scientific domains in the EU-27, associated countries, and globally with major players (US, India and China if data permits). The analysis thematically covers five pilot scientific domains—Astronomy & Physics, Materials Science, Earth Sciences, Life Sciences, and Social Sciences & Humanities—alongside cross-cutting AI research and innovation supporting the scientific process.

At the core of the methodology is the OpenAIRE Graph, which serves as a trusted, interoperable backbone linking publications, datasets, software, projects, organisations, and services. A dedicated data pipeline enables the collection, stratification, and enrichment of research outputs and funding information. This is complemented by the construction of a hierarchical AI Technology Ontology, automated detection of AI technologies in scientific texts, technology–application pairing, Technology Readiness Level (TRL) estimation, and multi-dimensional trend and ecosystem analyses.

In addition to landscape mapping, the deliverable defines the methodology for establishing the **SCIANCE Good Practices Registry** (see Section 4). Using a two-stage design—case identification and in-depth qualitative analysis based on a Context–Mechanism–Outcome framework—the registry documents empirically grounded examples of effective, responsible, and transferable AI-enabled scientific practices across diverse domains and institutional contexts.

Overall, this methodology ensures analytical rigor, transparency, and reproducibility, while enabling continuous updates and policy-relevant insights into the evolving European AI in Science ecosystem.

2 Mapping in the context of SCIANCE

SCIANCE aims to position Europe at the forefront of AI-enabled scientific research by delivering a Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda, an infrastructure roadmap, and a sustainable cooperation framework that brings together research communities, infrastructures, policymakers, and citizens in a vibrant European AI in Science ecosystem. In order to do so, SCIANCE will first provide a mapping of the European AI in Science landscape.

Figure 1 below illustrates the context of the mapping activities within the frame of SCIANCE:

Figure 1: Mapping the European AI in Science Landscape in the context of SCIANCE

In particular, the project will deliver a comprehensive overview of AI use in and for scientific research, combining systematic analyses across five pilot scientific domains with thematic reviews of cross-disciplinary AI innovations. It will also establish a consolidated mapping of European infrastructures / initiatives and a validated registry of good practices on AI-enabled science. As such, the mapping activities within SCIANCE are built upon the following pillars:

- **5 domain-specific state-of-the-art reviews on AI-enabled science**
- **1 state-of-the-art review on AI for Science research and innovations**
- **Interactive directory of >100 European initiatives/infrastructures**
- **Public registry of >50 community-validated good practices**

3 SCIANCE Mapping Methodology

As proposed in the SCIANCE Grant Agreement, the landscape analysis in T1.3 will employ a structured, semi-automated approach to identify and map key actors, infrastructures, and emerging trends in AI adoption across European scientific domains, building upon established sources and directories (e.g. AI-on-Demand ecosystem and the OpenAIRE Graph).

The analysis will start with the definition of inclusion criteria and the design of a structured knowledge model to organise and categorise information consistently about relevant AI infrastructures including computing resources (e.g. supercomputers, cloud services, edge computing), data infrastructures (e.g. open data platforms, data lakes, interoperability standards), AI testing and experimentation facilities, and other initiatives and projects (e.g. AI Factories, ADRA, ELLIS, CAIRNE, The GenAI Hub).

Alongside infrastructure mapping, the analysis will track emerging scientific trends in specific domains, such as the use of generative AI for materials discovery, LLMs in life sciences, AI-driven climate modelling, and the integration of AI in social sciences and humanities. In this respect, it will make use of the insights and results provided by T1.1 and T1.2.

This dual focus on AI infrastructure and scientific AI usage trends will highlight both adoption patterns and innovation frontiers, helping stakeholders align investments and strategies with scientific needs.

To ensure scalability, sustainability, and policy relevance, the analysis will leverage the OpenAIRE Graph (a global, trusted infrastructure interlinking publications, datasets, software, projects, organisations, and services, with high-quality curation for European research) as a continuously updated, interoperable backbone, enabling evidence-based insights for stakeholders.

3.1 Scope

The mapping conducted in the context of SCIANCE is conducted within the following clearly defined boundaries in terms of geography, domains and unit of analysis in order to ensure analytical focus and consistency.

3.1.1 Unit of analysis

Mapping in SCIANCE will be focused on the following three units of analysis:

3.1.1.1 Key actors of AI in Science

- Organisations: Research institutions, universities, and companies affiliated with researchers or projects in the targeted domains
- People: Individual researchers and creators involved in the research areas targeted

3.1.1.2 Relevant infrastructures for AI in Science

- Computing resources: supercomputers, cloud services, edge computing etc.
- Data infrastructures: open data platforms, data lakes, interoperability standards etc.
- Relevant initiatives and projects: AI testing and experimentation facilities, AI Factories, ADRA, ELLIS, CAIRNE, GenAI Hub etc.

3.1.1.3 Emerging trends in AI adoption in Science

- Insights, results provided by T1.1, i.e. state of the art for scientific research using AI for each pilot scientific area (domain-specific review of AI use for scientific research and potential research challenges (D1.1))
- Insights, results provided by T1.2, i.e. state of the art for AI research and innovations relevant for scientific research (review of AI methods, tools, and emerging technologies with high potential for scientific discovery, processes, and workflows (D1.2))

3.1.2 Geographical scope

Mapping of key actors of AI in Science and relevant infrastructures for AI in Science will be targeted at the EU-27 and dedicated associated countries participating in Horizon Europe (namely. UK, Switzerland, Norway, Iceland). In order to maximize the completeness and meaningfulness of the trends analysis in AI adoption in science, we will go beyond the EU-27 and associated countries and also cover U.S.A., China, and India where and if data permits.

3.1.3 Targeted domains

In line with the SCIANCE Grant Agreement, our mapping activities will be focussed on both (i) AI in the scientific pilot areas and (ii) AI research and innovations that support the scientific process.

3.1.3.1 AI in scientific pilot areas

SCIANCE targets five strategically selected pilot scientific areas that capitalise on Europe’s established scientific excellence and leading research infrastructures. These pilot areas present high potential to achieve transformative AI-enabled scientific breakthroughs, ensuring broad thematic coverage across all Horizon Europe Pillar II Clusters. The bullet list below provides examples of AI in Science Applications for each of the scientific pilot areas:

- Astronomy & Physics: Data reduction and signal processing, particle tracking and event reconstruction, anomaly detection, fast simulations and emulators, real-time analysis, uncertainty estimation and calibration, optimisation of telescope scheduling and quantum computing experiments, experimental design, and control (including quantum) etc.
- Materials Science: Property prediction from atomic/molecular structures, inverse materials design, catalyst activity and selectivity prediction, battery and energy material performance forecasting, polymer and soft matter design, alloy composition optimisation, defect and phase identification in microstructures, high-throughput robotic experiments, synthesis automation, microscopy image and real-time in situ experiment analysis, automated spectroscopy interpretation etc.
- Earth Sciences: Climate and environmental modelling, Earth observation and remote sensing analysis, natural disaster and extreme weather forecasting (and risk assessment), environmental monitoring and resource management, precision farming, Generative AI for agriculture, carbon stock estimation etc.
- Life Sciences: Drug discovery and molecular docking, gene expression and functional genomics, biomedical image analysis, protein folding and structure prediction, epidemiological modelling and disease prediction, health data integration, and personalised medicine etc.
- Social Sciences & Humanities: Text mining and semantic analysis, digital humanities (including art and cultural heritage analysis), simulation of economic and socio-political systems, bias detection and fairness assessment, opinion mining and social behaviour modelling, network analysis of social interactions etc.

3.1.3.2 AI research & innovation to support the scientific research process

Beyond domain-specific applications, SCIANCE will also cover cross-cutting AI for Science enablers, i.e. AI research and innovations that support the conduct of scientific tasks, processes, and workflows. This includes in particular the following aspects of the scientific process:

- Literature & Knowledge Discovery: Automated literature review, semantic search tools, hypothesis generation (LLMs), coresearchers with agentic AI etc.
- Experimental Design & Simulation: Optimal experiment design, simulation and modelling (ML), synthetic data etc.
- Data Collection & Processing: Sensor & imaging data, automated pre-processing, Edge-AI for fieldwork, Privacy preserving analytics etc.
- Data Analysis & Interpretation: Pattern recognition, predictive modelling, causal inference etc.
- Automation of Lab Workflows: Robotics & AI, high-throughput screening, closed-loop experimentation etc.
- Publication & Peer Review: Manuscript drafting, citation checking & fact verification, peer review support etc.
- Open Science & Reproducibility: Code & workflow analysis, metadata generation, knowledge preservation etc.
- Application & Policy Support: Translational research, risk assessment, ethics & governance etc.

3.2 Inclusion Criteria

In order to arrive at a meaningful identification of relevant actors, infrastructures and emerging trends in AI adoption across the targeted scientific domains, it is important to ensure their relevance when selecting them. Figure 2 below summarizes the corresponding inclusion criteria to be applied within the SCIANCE mapping exercise:

Table 1: Inclusion criteria for SCIANCE mapping methodology

Criterion	Description
Research relevance	Conducts and/or supports scientific research across one or more of the targeted domains (see 3.1 above for details) Enables creation, reuse, or evaluation of AI methods, models, or data
Persistent identifier	At least one of the following: URLs with versioning or stable IDs ROR (Research Organization Registry) - for hosting centres DOIs - for datasets, software, or services Where available: OpenAIRE internal identifiers
FAIR & Open Science compliance	Findable: Registered in catalogues, indexed with rich metadata Accessible: Open access or documented access policy Interoperable: Semantic metadata & standard vocabularies Reusable: Clear licensing, provenance, versioning
Relationship to OpenAIRE entities	Research products Data sources Organisations Projects Persons Communities
Readiness for technical integration	Preferable are: APIs or machine harvestable metadata endpoints are provided OAI-PMH, REST APIs, or SPARQL endpoints are supported Usage metrics or provenance info are available
Level of maturity	Operational or in late development (not just proposals) Backed by institutional or funded programs (long-term) Managed with governance, support and documentation

3.3 Data Pipeline Description

Once we have applied the criteria to survey candidate actors and infrastructures (see Section 5.2 above for inclusion criteria), mapping in SCIANCE will follow the basic data pipeline provided in Figure 3 below.

Figure 2: Overview of SCIANCE general data pipeline

It is important to note that all identified entities will need to be mapped to the OpenAIRE entity types. Figure 4 below provides examples of how different infrastructures are mapped to the existing OpenAIRE entities:

Table 2: Mapping of infrastructures to OpenAIRE entities

Example Infrastructure	OpenAIRE Graph Entity
AI infrastructure / platform	Organization and/or Service
Research centre / RI	Organization
National / European initiative	Project + Organization
Compute, data, AI service	Service or Software
Dataset repository	Datasource / Dataset
Individuals (optional)	Person (via ORCID)

With regard to the general data pipeline, it is also important to note that several steps within the above process can and will be supported using OpenAIRE Graph. For instance, the [OpenAIRE Validator service](#) facilitates the validation of metadata, i.e. testing for compatibility with Open AIRE Guidelines (see below). The following section (3.4 Model Development) will hence detail how OpenAIRE Graph is used for the overall model development.

3.4 Model Development

OpenAIRE contributes to the identification and mapping of key actors, infrastructures, and emerging trends in AI adoption by providing an automated pipeline with a human-in-the-loop (expert validation) that processes all relevant publications, projects, and funding calls to systematically map AI technology/method adoption across European scientific research. Figure 5 below summarizes the general process for the mapping starting with data collection up to trend analysis and the actors involved.

Figure 3: Model Development process using OpenAIRE

The following sub-sections will provide details about each step of the process.

3.4.1 Data collection & Stratification

In the context of Task T1.3 OpenAIRE mines publications, projects, and calls in order to provide:

- Organisational ecosystems from projects (RPOs/RFOs, networks, geography)
- Emerging trends per pilot domain (technology adoption dynamics by discipline)
- Technology maturity assessment (TRL estimation - research-stage vs. deployment-ready)
- Organizational ecosystems from projects (RPOs/RFOs, geography)
- Funding priorities from calls vs. research execution

3.4.1.1 Data collection and sources

As regards the data sources, while **OpenAIRE Graph** provides publication metadata (titles, abstracts, FoS classifications) and project/call identifiers, **external sources** are required for full-text project descriptions and funding call texts (or we use extrapolation via project-publications). In SCIANCE, data collection is carried out through a combination of direct crawling, inference from linked publications, and potential access to partner-maintained databases, in order to ensure broad and robust coverage of key actors, infrastructures and trends for AI in Science.

- Direct crawling from external sources: Direct crawling is used to retrieve project descriptions from external sources, including the Open Data Portal for EU-funded projects and national funder databases. In parallel, funding call texts are collected from sources such as the Funding & Tenders Portal for Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020, national research council websites, and archival resources such as ESFRI. These sources provide authoritative and up-to-date information on funding priorities, project objectives, and expected outcomes.

- Inference from resulting publications: In addition to direct data acquisition, technology and application information is inferred from publications that are linked to specific projects or funding calls. Relevant publications are analysed to extract AI technology and application mentions, and the resulting publication-level information is aggregated to the corresponding project or call level. Although this approach is less direct than analysing project or call texts themselves, it benefits from the extensive coverage of scientific publications available through the OpenAIRE Graph, thereby increasing recall and contextual depth.
- Partner databases: Finally, the process may be complemented by direct access to structured project, call and especially infrastructure databases provided by consortium partners. Such access would enable the integration of high-quality, structured metadata that may not be publicly available or easily crawlable. The specific partner databases and access modalities are to be defined, but their inclusion would further enhance data completeness, consistency, and validation across sources.

3.4.1.2 Domain stratification and validation

To enable systematic analysis across the targeted scientific pilot domains, publications and projects are stratified into **five SCIANCE pilot areas**, complemented by a cross-cutting **Artificial Intelligence (AI) domain**, using **Field of Science (FoS) classifications** as the primary semantic alignment mechanism. Unlike the domain pilot areas, the AI pilot is not restricted to a single FoS domain but focuses on identifying AI-related methodologies, workflows, and infrastructures embedded within research activities in all scientific areas. This stratification ensures disciplinary relevance while preserving cross-domain comparability within the OpenAIRE Graph. Figure 6 below shows how the areas targeted by SCIANCE relate to the FoS classification to be used for domain stratification.

Table 3: SCIANCE target domains and FoS classifications

SCIANCE pilot area	Corresponding FoS classification
Astronomy & Fundamental Physics	covering Physical Sciences and Space Sciences FoS categories
Materials Science	covering Materials Engineering and Chemical Science
Earth Sciences	covering Earth and Environmental Sciences and Atmospheric Sciences
Life Sciences	covering Biological, Medical, Health, and Agricultural Sciences
Social Sciences & Humanities (SSH)	covering Social Sciences, Humanities, and Arts
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	covering Computer and Information Sciences

The **stratification workflow** is implemented through a structured, reproducible process leveraging the OpenAIRE Graph:

- FoS-based Filtering: The OpenAIRE Graph is queried using curated sets of FoS codes corresponding to each pilot area. Publications and projects tagged with one or more of these FoS classifications are selected for inclusion.
- Extraction of Project and Call Identifiers: For the selected records, persistent project and call identifiers (e.g. OpenAIRE project IDs, funder call identifiers) are extracted to enable traceability, aggregation, and linkage across funding, outputs, and infrastructures.
- Retrieval of Full-Text Descriptions: Full-text content is retrieved where available, including (i) Project abstracts and descriptions and (ii) Publication full texts or extended abstracts. Retrieval is performed using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs, OpenAIRE IDs) and validated access routes.
- Linkage Back to Graph Entities: Retrieved textual content is systematically linked back to the corresponding OpenAIRE Graph entities (projects, publications) via persistent identifiers, ensuring bidirectional traceability between text corpora and graph metadata.
- Pilot-Specific Corpus Construction: Separate text corpora are constructed for each pilot area. This enables domain-aware analysis, accounting for disciplinary terminology, research practices, and AI usage patterns specific to each scientific field.
- Multi-label Handling: Publications and projects classified under multiple FoS categories are included in all relevant pilot areas. This multi-label approach preserves interdisciplinary research signals and avoids artificial domain partitioning.

3.4.1.3 Quality assurance and validation

To ensure robustness, transparency, and reproducibility, multiple quality control measures are applied throughout the workflow:

- Automated retrieval processes are validated through systematic sampling and manual inspection
- Records with missing, incomplete, or low-quality textual content are flagged for exclusion or downstream treatment

- Coverage metrics are calculated and documented for each pilot area, including:
 - Proportion of records with full-text availability
 - Distribution across FoS categories and countries
- Methodological choices (e.g. inclusion thresholds, retrieval strategies) explicitly prioritize data quality, completeness, and semantic consistency over raw volume

Overall, this approach ensures that each pilot corpus is analytically reliable, semantically coherent, and fully traceable to the OpenAIRE Graph, providing a solid foundation for cross-domain and AI-focused analyses.

3.4.2 AI Technology Ontology Construction

The objective of this step is to construct a comprehensive, hierarchical ontology of AI technologies, understood here as AI methods, that are relevant to scientific research across domains. The ontology is designed to support the systematic identification, classification, and analysis of AI usage within the scientific process, enabling consistent annotation and cross-domain comparability.

3.4.2.1 Ontology scope and structure

Building on existing evidence¹, the SCIANCE ontology will be organised as a **multi-level hierarchy**, capturing both foundational AI concepts and domain-specific methodological variants. It is structured around the following high-level categories summarized in Figure 6 below:

Table 4: Potential structure of ontology

Core Architectures
Fundamental model architectures that underpin modern AI systems, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Transformers, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), Foundation Models, and Large Language Models (LLMs)
Learning Paradigms
Training and learning strategies that define how models acquire knowledge, such as self-supervised learning, transfer learning, reinforcement learning, federated learning, and few-shot learning.
Domain-Aware Methods
Methods explicitly designed to incorporate scientific knowledge or constraints, including <i>Physics-Informed Neural Networks</i> , <i>symmetry-aware models</i> , and <i>Bayesian optimisation techniques</i> .
Generative and Simulation Models
AI approaches used for data generation, simulation, and surrogate modelling, including Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), diffusion models, neural operators, and surrogate models.
Trustworthy AI Methods
Techniques addressing robustness, transparency, and reliability, such as uncertainty estimation, explainability methods, causal inference, and knowledge graph-based approaches.

This structure enables both high-level aggregation and fine-grained methodological analysis across scientific domains.

3.4.2.2 Process for ontology construction

The ontology construction follows a hybrid expert-assisted and automated approach:

- Initial Seeding: The ontology is seeded using authoritative sources, including SCIANCE results from T1.1–1.3, major AI survey papers, and domain-specific methodological reviews. This ensures broad coverage of established and emerging AI methods used in scientific research.
- Terminology Expansion: Large Language Models (LLMs) are employed to generate variant expressions, abbreviations, and synonyms for each method. For example, “*convolutional neural network*” is expanded to include “*CNN*” and “*ConvNet*”. This step supports robust text mining and reduces terminological bias across domains.
- Hierarchical Structuring: Explicit parent-child relationships are defined to reflect conceptual and technical dependencies. For instance, *Transformer* models are linked to specialised variants such as *Vision Transformer* and *BERT*. This hierarchical organisation supports semantic reasoning and method aggregation.
- Iterative Refinement: The ontology is iteratively refined through feedback from the project consortium, allowing continuous adjustment based on domain relevance, emerging methods, and analytical needs.

¹ See, for instance, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2458267c-08df-11ee-b12e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>, <https://github.com/berkeleybop/artificial-intelligence-ontology>

3.4.2.3 Quality assurance and validation

In SCIANCE, the ontology validation combines expert review and cross-referencing:

- Domain experts assess coverage and relevance for each scientific pilot area (initially in the context of the workshops in WP2/WP3, at a later stage in the context of the AISWG in WP6/7), ensuring that domain-specific AI methods are adequately represented.
- The resulting ontology is cross-validated against established AI taxonomies and classifications, ensuring conceptual consistency and alignment with community standards.

Through this process, the ontology achieves both methodological completeness and semantic precision, making it suitable for large-scale, domain-aware analysis of AI usage in scientific research.

3.4.3 Automated Technology Detection

The objective of the automated technology detection is to identify and classify mentions of artificial intelligence technologies within publication abstracts, project descriptions, and funding call texts.

3.4.3.1 Model design

The approach relies on fine-tuned transformer-based language models, including SciBERT, PubMedBERT, and other domain-adapted BERT variants, which are well suited to scientific and technical text. Because individual documents may reference multiple AI technologies, the task is formulated as a multi-label classification problem, and the system assigns confidence scores to each detected technology mention.

3.4.3.2 Training approach

The training strategy combines automated and expert-driven methods to ensure both coverage and accuracy. Initially, silver-standard training labels are generated through ontology-based distant supervision, enabling large-scale weakly labelled data. Active learning techniques are then applied to capture implicit or indirect technology references, such as interpreting phrases like “message-passing on graphs” as mentions of Graph Neural Networks. To further improve quality, gold-standard annotations are produced by domain experts and stratified by pilot area, providing high-quality reference data for model refinement and evaluation.

3.4.3.3 Content coverage

The processing scope varies by document type. For publications, the analysis focuses on titles and abstracts. For projects, the full textual descriptions are processed, including objectives and expected impacts. For funding calls, the system analyses sections describing the scope, objectives, and expected outcomes.

3.4.3.4 Detection of emerging technologies

In addition to identifying predefined AI technologies, the process also supports the detection of emerging technologies. Unsupervised pattern extraction methods are used to identify novel or evolving terminology in the corpus. These candidate terms are subsequently reviewed and validated by experts, and approved concepts may be added to the underlying ontology.

3.4.3.5 Quality assurance and validation

Quality assurance is achieved through a comprehensive evaluation framework. Precision, recall, and F1-scores are calculated for each technology category and pilot area to assess model performance. In parallel, inter-annotator agreement is measured on expert-validated datasets to ensure consistency and reliability in the annotation process. Expert validation of the data sets will initially take place in the context of the workshops/workshop preparation in WP2/WP3, at a later stage in the context of the AISWG in WP6/7.

3.4.4 Technology application pairing

The objective of this process is to extract and analyse relationships between artificial intelligence technologies and their scientific applications in order to produce a differential mapping for Task T1.2. The goal is to understand how specific AI methods are linked to particular application areas across different types of research and funding documents.

3.4.4.1 Method

For each AI technology detected in a document, the system extracts the surrounding textual context, typically spanning two sentences before and after the mention. Within this context, predefined linguistic patterns are used to identify technology–application relationships. These patterns include constructions such as “T for X,” “T to solve Y,” and “using T in Z,” as well as causal or enabling formulations like “T enables W” or “T accelerates V,” and domain-oriented expressions such as “applying T to domain D.”

Dependency parsing techniques are then applied to the extracted sentences to identify and isolate the relevant application noun phrases. For example, in the phrase “CNNs for protein structure prediction,” the system extracts “protein structure prediction” as the application associated with convolutional neural networks. To improve precision, semantic filtering is performed to remove overly generic or non-informative terms. The remaining application phrases are validated against established domain vocabularies, such as MeSH and NASA ADS, to ensure relevance and consistency.

Each extracted technology–application pair inherits an existing Field of Science (FoS) classification, which enables automatic mapping to the appropriate pilot area. This supports structured aggregation and comparison across domains.

3.4.4.2 Comparative analysis

A comparative analysis is then conducted across different document types. Funding calls are analysed to capture the applications that funders explicitly request or prioritize. Project descriptions are examined to identify the applications that researchers propose to pursue. Publications are analysed to determine the applications that researchers ultimately deliver in their scientific outputs. Comparing these three sources makes it possible to identify areas of alignment as well as gaps between funder priorities, planned research activities, and realized research outcomes.

3.4.4.3 Quality assurance and validation

Quality assurance is ensured through a combination of automated and manual checks. A sample-based manual validation is performed, typically involving 100 technology–application pairs per pilot area. In addition, domain experts review high-frequency pairs to confirm their correctness and interpretability, ensuring that the resulting mappings are reliable and suitable for reporting and downstream analysis. As before, SCIANCE will benefit from the support of experts initially in the context of the workshops/workshop preparation in WP2/WP3, at a later stage in the context of the AISWG in WP6/7.

3.4.5 Technology readiness level estimation

The objective of this process is to estimate the maturity level of AI technologies in order to distinguish methods that are still at the research stage from those that are ready for deployment. This assessment of the so-called Technology Readiness Level (TRL) supports a structured understanding of how close different AI approaches are to real-world operational use.

3.4.5.1 Signals

The estimation relies on multiple complementary signals. Linguistic cues in the text are used to infer maturity levels, ranging from early-stage expressions such as “proof of concept,” through intermediate indicators like “validated on benchmarks,” to mature-stage formulations including “operational use” or “deployed in production.” In addition, publication and citation patterns are analysed, taking into account factors such as the prestige of publication venues and the growth of citations over time, which serve as proxies for community uptake and validation.

3.4.5.2 Method

The methodology combines rule-based and supervised learning approaches. Explicit indicators of Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) are first captured through rule-based classification, targeting documents that directly reference maturity stages. In parallel, supervised classifiers are trained on corpora where TRL information is explicitly stated, such as project reports and technical papers. These models leverage a set of features that includes linguistic patterns, methodological indicators, and publication metadata.

The output of the process consists of estimated TRL values, expressed either on a detailed 1–9 scale or as aggregated categories such as Low, Medium, and High maturity. Each estimate is accompanied by a confidence score, and cases with low confidence are automatically flagged for manual review.

3.4.5.3 Quality assurance and validation

Validation is carried out through expert assessment of sampled results, stratified by pilot area and technology. Where available, the generated estimates are also compared against existing TRL assessments to measure concordance and ensure the robustness and credibility of the maturity classification.

3.4.6 Trend analysis and ecosystem mapping

This part of the process focuses on trend analysis and ecosystem mapping in order to understand adoption dynamics, growth trajectories, and the organisational landscape surrounding AI technologies in and for science. As indicated above in section 3.1.2 Geographical scope, while the ecosystem mapping will be focussed on the EU-27 and associated countries, the trends analysis in AI adoption across scientific domains will go beyond if and where data permits and also cover major players (e.g. US, India and China). The objective is to provide a comprehensive, data-driven view of how technologies evolve over time, spread across domains, and are supported by research and funding ecosystems.

3.4.6.1 Temporal trends (per technology, per pilot area)

Temporal trend analysis is conducted for each technology and pilot area. Adoption curves are constructed using publication and project counts over time to illustrate uptake and diffusion patterns. Growth dynamics are quantified through measures such as compound annual growth rates, exponential trend fitting, and change-point detection to identify periods of acceleration or slowdown. In parallel, maturity trajectories are analysed by tracking the evolution of Technology Readiness Levels over time. These signals are combined to detect hype-cycle patterns, characterized by phases of rapid growth followed by stabilization, plateauing, or decline.

3.4.6.2 Cross-domain analysis

Cross-domain analysis examines how AI technologies diffuse across different pilot areas. This includes identifying whether technologies originate in one domain and later spread to others, as well as distinguishing between domain-specific methods and general-purpose technologies based on the breadth of their adoption. Interdisciplinary activity is captured through the co-occurrence of multiple Fields of Science within single publications, indicating cross-domain integration. The analysis also traces technology transfer pathways, such as the migration of computer vision methods into application areas like medical imaging.

3.4.6.3 Organisational ecosystem

The organisational ecosystem is mapped by extracting affiliation information from publications and project documentation. This includes in particular the identification of companies (and their types, e.g. limited company, corporation etc.) as opposed to different types of public sector organisations (e.g. universities). This procedure does not only enable the identification of key players, including research performing organizations and research funding organizations, for each technology and pilot area, but also gives an idea to what extent research was relevant to the private sector. Collaboration structures are analysed through co-authorship networks and consortium partnerships, revealing patterns of cooperation and knowledge exchange. Geographic distributions are also examined to highlight country-level and regional concentrations of activity.

3.4.6.4 Technology co-occurrence

In addition, technology co-occurrence analysis is performed to understand how AI methods are combined in practice. Frequently occurring technology combinations, such as the joint use of convolutional neural networks and transfer learning, are identified. The analysis captures the emergence of multi-modal AI pipelines and tracks how technology stacks evolve over time, providing insight into increasing methodological complexity and integration.

4 SCIANCE Good Practices Registry

This section outlines the methodology employed to develop the registry of good practices in AI-enabled science (Task 1.4). This approach involves collecting systematic evidence, co-creating good-practice criteria with stakeholders, and conducting qualitative case analyses to identify, examine and document examples of AI in science and AI for science that are grounded in evidence, across diverse scientific domains and institutional contexts.

The methodology follows a two-stage design. Stage 1 involves identifying and selecting cases through desk-based research, bottom-up nominations, and co-creating shared criteria to guide the scope and relevance of candidate practices. Stage 2 involves an in-depth, qualitative analysis of the shortlisted cases, using a Context–Mechanism–Outcome (hereafter - CMO) framework to explain how AI-enabled practices operate under specific conditions, and the resulting epistemic, ethical, legal and organisational effects.

This analysis draws on multiple sources, including publicly available documentation and structured interviews with representatives of the practices. It is also iteratively triangulated with the project's state-of-the-art and mapping activities (Tasks 1.1–1.3). The findings are synthesised into standardised case descriptions and consolidated in **the Good Practices Registry for the Digital Hub**.

Alongside the development of the registry and the production of cross-domain knowledge to support priority-setting and decision-making related to RAISE and the SRIA, the initiative also pursues a parallel methodological objective. Specifically, it seeks to develop and refine **a replicable process** for the collection, analysis, verification, and publication of good practices, with the aim of making this activity sustainable beyond the project lifecycle. This involves establishing transparent procedures, shared criteria, and standardised templates that can support the continuous identification and documentation of practices across institutional contexts. In this way, **the registry is conceived not only as a knowledge resource but also as a foundation for a permanent good-practice monitoring and learning mechanism.**

4.1 Concept

Good practices in AI-enabled science are empirically observed socio-technical configurations of AI use which activate desirable epistemic, ethical, legal and organisational outcomes across the research life cycle of scientific knowledge production in specific contexts.

Each good practice initially centres on an AI-driven method, approach, or tool employed by an individual or team within a project or informal collaboration and situated in an institutionalised setting (e.g. private enterprises, start-ups, research infrastructures, organisations, universities, or NGOs). Although the focus is on successful practices, the analysis also incorporates lessons learned from unsuccessful applications in various organisational contexts.

These practices fall into two broad domains: AI in science and AI for scientific processes and workflows, and grasp:

- Theory development, hypothesis building and knowledge discovery;
- Data collection, processing and FAIRification (data management);
- Analysis and interpretation;
- Experimental design and simulation;
- Workflow, lab automation and collaboration;
- Publication and open science;
- Application and policy support.

4.2 Scope & Contexts Representation

Geographical scope is limited to 27 EU member states and dedicated associated countries (namely, UK, Switzerland, Norway).

The scope of practice selection is driven by the contexts in which practices are implemented. These contexts are captured through four categories:

- Institutional type (Industry/Innovation; Research/HEI; NGO: Research infrastructures);
- Scientific domain (Astronomy & Physics; Earth Sciences; Materials Sciences; Life Sciences; Social Science & Humanities; Cross-domain);
- Data governance (Open; Managed; Restricted);
- Resource conditions (High; Moderate; Constrained).

Figure 7 below provides an overview of the context categories SCIANCE uses, namely institutional type, data governance regime, and resource conditions.

Table 5: Description of context categories

Category	Description
Institutional type	
Industry & Innovation	R&D-oriented and AI companies, SMEs, and startups developing or implementing technological solutions.
Research institutes & higher education institutions	Public or private higher education institutions and standalone research organisations primarily engaged in scientific research and knowledge production.
Non-profit research organisations (NGOs)	Research-focused entities without profit-oriented business models, including civil society organisations and community-based research initiatives.
Research infrastructures	Organisations that develop, operate, or coordinate shared AI research infrastructures, including high-performance computing centres, data infrastructure providers, AI testing and experimentation facilities, and collaborative infrastructure initiatives and networks.
Data governance regime	
Open data	Data are openly accessible, reusable, and auditable.
Managed-access data	Data are shared under controlled conditions (e.g. trusted research environments), balancing openness with legal and ethical constraints.
Restricted / sensitive data	Access limited due to privacy, security, or commercial concerns, requiring strong compliance and oversight.
Resource conditions	
High-resource environments	Access to advanced computing infrastructure, large datasets, specialised AI expertise, and sustained funding.
Moderate-resource environments	Limited computing capacity and expertise; reliance on shared infrastructure, external tools, or project-based funding.
Resource-constrained environments	Minimal infrastructure and funding; reliance on frugal AI approaches, lightweight models, and adaptive reuse of tools.

The initial allocation of cases to context categories is conducted at the identification stage (section 4.3.1.). This allocation is preliminary and will be further clarified and refined during the analytical stage (section 4.3.2).

The distribution of good practices is fixed only by scientific domain (seven cases per pilot domain and seven cross-domain cases). At the same time, the final good practice registry will ensure coverage across dimensions of the listed contextual categories.

4.3 Methodology

The good-practice registry is developed through two methodological stages: (1) identification and selection, and (2) analysis. Stage 1 combines desk-based research, bottom-up nominations by partners and stakeholders (relevant expert and science networks, AISWG members), and a co-creative process with project partners to develop criteria for good practices.

Stage 2 adopts a realist perspective on practice deployment, operationalised through a CMO framework. It applies qualitative case study methods to examine how practices function under specific conditions and what outcomes they generate. The analysis draws on multiple sources, including publicly available documentation (e.g., scientific publications and organisational materials) and structured interviews with practice representatives. The overall methodological pipeline is illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 4: Methodological pipeline for the good practice registry

4.3.1 Good practice identification and selection

Stage 1 establishes a shared understanding of what constitutes a “good practice” in AI-enabled science through the co-creation of interpretive criteria. In parallel, it identifies and screens candidate cases to produce a shortlist that is empirically analysable, feasible to document and present, and substantively relevant to the registry’s scope. This stage focuses on sampling and feasibility rather than evaluative judgement, preparing cases for in-depth analysis in Stage 2.

4.3.1.1 Co-creation of good practice criteria

The criteria for good practices in AI-enabled science are developed through a structured co-creation process with project partners. This process used a modified Real-Time Delphi approach involving one session. Building on a set of preliminary dimensions grounded in analysis - including impact, productivity, transferability, transparency, ethical and legal responsibility, openness, trustworthiness and frugality (see Figure 9 below) - participants engaged in an online iterative consultation and a final consensus discussion.

For each dimension, contributors were invited to propose and refine qualitative indicators that clarified how the criterion might manifest in practice. Participants then rated these indicators using a scale to assess their relative **importance and clarity**. They then received anonymised and aggregated feedback.

At this stage, the criteria function as **interpretive guidelines** to support shared understanding and consistent judgement across scientific domains; they are not used to score or rank practices.

Table 6: Criteria dimensions for identifying and selection of good practices in AI-enabled science

Criterion	Description
Impact	Demonstrable contribution to scientific knowledge production
Productivity	Evidence of increased efficiency, timeliness, or capacity of research activities without compromising scientific quality.
Openness & Transferability (inc. FAIR)	Degree to which data, metadata, models, code, and workflows are documented, standardised, and structured to enable discovery, access, interoperability, reuse, and adaptation across domains and institutional contexts (e.g., persistent identifiers, rich metadata, standard formats, implementation guidance).
Transparency & Trustworthiness	Explicit specification of where, how, and for what purposes AI systems are used within research workflows.
Ethical awareness	Identification of ethical risks and regulatory requirements, together with documented mitigation and compliance strategies.
Frugality	Alignment between resource investments and scientific objectives; cost-effective and context-sensitive deployment of AI solutions.

4.3.1.2 Case identification (building the longlist)

Desk-research identification of candidate cases. An initial pool of candidate cases is identified through desk research focusing on documented uses of AI in scientific research (AI in Science) and in research-related processes and infrastructures (AI for Science). This process draws on multiple complementary sources, including:

- white papers, policy reports, and strategy documents at EU, national, and international levels (including outputs from international organisations such as the OECD);
- scientific literature and dedicated studies on the use of AI in scientific research;
- publicly available information at the websites of organisations with a demonstrated engagement in AI research and development, as evidenced through patents, publications, or research infrastructure activities;
- Identification via quantitative signals (multi-technology integration, high-impact publications, open science evidence) from parallel T1.3 mapping activities.

Bottom-up nomination. In parallel with desk-based identification, candidate cases are also identified through a bottom-up nomination process involving project partners, networks and AISWG members. They are invited to nominate relevant AI-enabled practices based on their professional expertise. Nominations are collected through online form and direct consultations.

The long list of candidate cases includes information on their context categories, which will be refined during the analytical stage. It also contains an initial description of each case and/or sources of information and **a preliminary check against the agreed criteria**. Key sources used for case identification and a brief case summary are included to facilitate further review.

4.3.1.3 Shortlisting (feasibility and relevance screening)

Shortlisting applies eligibility and feasibility criteria:

- availability of verifiable documentation;
- feasibility of public presentation;
- reasonable access to interviewees.

In addition, the co-created good-practice criteria are used only as **a relevance screen** (i.e., to confirm that the practice plausibly relates to one or more criterion dimensions and fits the registry scope). They are not applied as an approval threshold at this stage because outcomes and mechanisms cannot yet be established empirically.

4.3.1.4 Verification & validation

Shortlisted cases are cross-checked against the project’s mapping results (Tasks 1.1–1.3) to ensure consistency with system-level patterns and to mitigate selection bias. This step verifies that the sample (42-50 cases) adequately reflects the diversity of domains, institutional settings, and AI applications identified across the broader landscape.

The shortlist is then reviewed by project partners and, if applicable, AI Working Group members based on their domain expertise and scientific workflow experience. The review focuses on accuracy, feasibility, and relevance to the registry scope, and may identify additional candidates. All additional cases undergo the same screening procedures.

4.3.2 Analysis

The analytical stage explains how and under what conditions AI-enabled practices generate epistemic, ethical, legal, and organisational outcomes. The analysis adopts a realist-informed approach structured around the CMO framework, enabling systematic comparison across heterogeneous scientific and organisational settings.

The analytical process follows an abductive logic, iteratively combining inductive insights from empirical materials with deductive engagement with existing conceptual frameworks and findings from the project's state-of-the-art and mapping tasks.

4.3.2.1 Data Sources

The analysis of each case draws on multiple, complementary data sources to ensure analytical depth and robustness:

1) Desk-research materials, including publicly available information from official organisational websites; descriptions of AI-enabled tools, methods, and research infrastructures; patent documentation; scientific publications; and working papers.

2) Structured interviews with one or more representatives of the organisations or teams involved in the development, implementation, governance, or use of the identified AI-enabled practices (e.g. individual researchers, research managers, infrastructure providers, or policy-relevant stakeholders). Interviews may be conducted with single participants or with multiple actors representing a team or organisational unit.

Participation in interviews is based on prior informed consent. Participants are informed about the purpose of the study, the nature of data collected, the intended use of the data. All interviews are audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim. *No raw audio recordings or identifiable interview data are uploaded to external LLM-based services.*

Data collection is guided by a common set of thematic domains reflected in both the desk-review template and the structured interview guide. They include:

- teamwork and skill profiles;
- interdisciplinary collaboration practices;
- ethical oversight, governance, and regulatory compliance;
- FAIR data sharing infrastructures;
- access to hardware and computing resources;
- software ecosystems, platforms.

4.3.2.2 Analytical Procedures

All empirical materials are coded within the CMO framework. Data analysis is conducted through a structured coding process organised around CMO framework. All empirical materials are systematically coded into three primary analytical domains.

Context codes follow predefined categories derived from the study's analytical scope, including institutional type, scientific domain, data governance arrangements, and resource conditions, enabling systematic comparison across cases.

Mechanisms are identified primarily through inductive coding to capture the generative processes through which AI is integrated into research practice. These include such code families as organisational routines, decision-making structures, technical configurations, coordination practices, enabling factors, and constraints that shape how AI tools influence scientific work. The co-created good-practice criteria inform this analysis as interpretive lenses where relevant, particularly for dimensions such as transparency, ethical awareness, openness, and frugality.

Outcomes capture both intended and unintended epistemic, organisational, legal, and ethical effects of the practice. At this stage, the criteria provide a structured basis for assessing the quality and consequences of observed results (e.g., impact on knowledge production, productivity gains, responsible use, or transferability).

Attention is paid to *negative and unintended outcomes, as well as to unsuccessful or constraining mechanisms*, in order to mitigate success bias and to capture the full range of implications associated with AI-enabled scientific practices.

Both within-case and cross-case analyses are applied to identify recurring CMO configurations and to distinguish context-specific mechanisms from those that demonstrate potential for transferability across scientific domains and institutional settings. The results of the analysis for each case are presented using a common template (see Annex).

4.3.2.3 The Use of LLMs for Data Analysis

To support the efficient handling of qualitative materials, LLMs are to be employed to assist with text categorisation and preliminary code assignment. No personal or sensitive data are transferred to non-compliant external AI services. Where LLMs are applied, they operate exclusively on pseudonymised or fully anonymised data. All machine-assisted coding outputs are subject to mandatory manual review and validation by the research team to ensure methodological consistency, analytical reliability, and interpretive accuracy. LLM-supported analysis will not replace human judgement at any stage of the analytical process.

4.3.2.4 Validation and Quality Assurance

Analytical results undergo a structured validation process prior to finalisation. Draft case profiles and cross-case findings are reviewed by project partners to verify factual accuracy, clarify contextual details, and provide domain-specific feedback.

5 Annex – Good Practice Registry Template

Title:
Author(s), organisation(s), and country:
<p>Context</p> <p>Institutional type: <input type="checkbox"/> Industry/Innovation <input type="checkbox"/> Research/HEI <input type="checkbox"/> NGO <input type="checkbox"/> Research infrastructure</p> <p>Scientific domain: <input type="checkbox"/> Astronomy & Physics <input type="checkbox"/> Earth Sciences <input type="checkbox"/> Materials Sciences <input type="checkbox"/> Life Sciences <input type="checkbox"/> Social Science & Humanities <input type="checkbox"/> Cross-domain</p> <p>Data governance: <input type="checkbox"/> Open <input type="checkbox"/> Managed <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted</p> <p>Resource conditions: <input type="checkbox"/> High <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Constrained</p>
<p>Workflow integration (type of AI use)</p> <p>Brief narrative explanation of how AI is integrated into the workflow (relevant categories indicated):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theory development, hypothesis building and knowledge discovery • Data collection, processing and FAIRification (data management) • Analysis and interpretation • Experimental design and simulation • Workflow, lab automation and collaboration • Publication and open science • Application and policy support
<p>Mechanisms - enabling conditions (how the practice works)</p> <p>A structured narrative, addressing the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team composition and skill profiles • Interdisciplinary collaboration practices • Ethical oversight and compliance procedures • Governance and accountability measures • Technical and infrastructural conditions • Hardware/compute access (HPC, GPUs, etc) • Software ecosystems, platforms, repositories, tools, support services
<p>Outcomes - good-practice assessment (why it is good)</p> <p>A structured narrative, addressing the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact on knowledge production • Productivity • Openness & transferability • Transparency & responsible use • Frugality